

ON THE PHOTOBROMINATION OF CINNAMIC ACID IN ULTRAVIOLET LIGHT OF 254μ .

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The kinetics and mechanism of the bromination of cinnamic acid in ultraviolet light of 254μ in solution of carbon tetrachloride have been studied in details. Results which have been found are quite different from those found with visible light by various workers. The reaction is unimolecular with respect to bromine as well as with respect to cinnamic acid. The velocity constant is directly proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed by cinnamic acid and is independent of the nature of polarisation of light. The temperature coefficient and the quantum efficiency are more than unity. A mechanism involving activated cinnamic acid molecules has been suggested.

The photobromination of cinnamic acid and stilbene has been investigated by various workers, notably by Berthoud and Béraueck (*J. chim. phys.*, 1927, 24, 213) and by Ghosh and Purakayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 261; 1927, 4, 409; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, B, 9, 154) in non-polar solvents like CCl_4 , CS_2 , etc. It is generally agreed that in these photobrominations in visible light, bromine atoms are the photoactive agents which start a chain reaction and the velocity is given by the equation,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} = k_3[\text{Br}_2] \frac{\sqrt{k_1 I}}{k_2} \cdot \frac{k_5[A]}{k_4 + k_5[A]}.$$

The object of the present investigation was to find out whether any bromination could be carried out in ultraviolet light of wave-length 254μ which is very slightly absorbed by bromine, but completely absorbed by cinnamic acid in extremely dilute solutions.

Ghosh and Biswas (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1924, 30, 97) have investigated the molecular extinction coefficients of cinnamic acid in wave-length 254μ and found it to be about 10,000. Thus in 254μ cinnamic acid is the absorbing substance while bromine acts as an acceptor molecule.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement was the same as was described by the authors in previous works (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, B, 32, 145; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 257) with a few alterations:—(a) The reaction cell was 1.8 cm. $\times$ 1.8 cm. $\times$ 0.5 cm. thick and made of plane quartz plates fused into one another with a stopper at the top; (b) the spectral region 254μ was isolated with the help of a quartz cylindrical cell containing a strong solution of bromine (0.2M) in CCl_4 placed in front of the window between the lens and the reaction cell.

Merck's extra pure cinnamic acid further purified by crystallisation and Merck's extra pure "reagent" bromine were used throughout. Merck's extra pure CCl_4 further purified by distillation over fused CaCl_2 was used.

Determination of the Velocity of Reaction.—The velocity of the reaction was determined by pipetting out 0.32 c.c. of the reaction mixture and titrating iodometrically with 0.01N-thio-sulphate solution by means of a microburette. The reactions were carried out at 31° and 41°.

The light passing through the bromine filter contains much red light which was found to be not altogether ineffective in bringing about the photochemical bromination of cinnamic acid. To eliminate the effect of red light the following arrangement was made. Two experiments were done for each composition of the reaction mixture. One, with the total light emerging through three quartz cells containing pure water, 0.2M bromine solution in CCl_4 and lastly, pure

carbon tetrachloride placed in series; the other, with the light emerging through three quartz cells in series containing pure water, 0.2M bromine solution in CCl₄, and lastly a strong solution of cinnamic acid in CCl₄ (0.25M). In the first case the velocity of reaction was due to radiation 254 μμ and to red light. In the second case it was due to red light only as the cinnamic acid of 0.25M strength completely absorbed the 254 μμ radiation.

Measurement of Intensity.—The intensity of radiation (254 μμ) absorbed by the cinnamic acid solution was measured by means of a Moll galvanometer and Moll thermopile, calibrated by means of a standard lamp supplied by the "Bureau of Standards". The intensity was measured by noting the deflections when the light passed (a) through bromine filter alone, and (b) bromine filter + cinnamic acid filter. The difference in deflections in the two cases gave the intensity of 254 μμ radiation absorbed by the cinnamic acid.

All the experiments in this investigation were finished within one hour of the exposure during which no dark reaction was observed between cinnamic acid and bromine at temperatures between 31° and 41°.

The experimental data are recorded in Tables I to V. The velocity constant in this investigation was calculated according to the simple monomolecular equation, viz.,

$$k_0 = \frac{2.3}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$$

where *a* is the initial concentration of bromine in g. mols. per litre and *x*, the change in concentration of bromine in time *t* minutes. The experimental data did not fit any other equation.

One typical experiment is recorded below.

TABLE I.

a = 0.102M. *b* (initial conc. of cinnamic acid) = 0.05M. *I*_{abs} (number of quanta absorbed by cinnamic acid per c.c. per sec.) = 19.4 × 10¹³. λ = 254 μμ. θ (temp.) = 31°

<i>t</i> .	<i>T</i> ₁ .	<i>T</i> ₂ .	<i>T</i> ₃ .	<i>k</i> ₀ × 10 ⁴	<i>γ</i>
20	0.85	0.56	0.29	22.6	11.8

*T*₁ = titre difference in c.c. of 0.01N-thiosulphate corresponding to 0.32 c.c. of the reaction mixture when exposed to light passing through bromine filter for *t* minutes; *T*₂ = titre difference in c.c. of 0.01N-thiosulphate corresponding to 0.32 c.c. of the reaction mixture when exposed to light passing through bromine filter and cinnamic acid filter in series in time *t* minutes; *T*₃ = titre difference in c.c. of 0.01N-thiosulphate corresponding to 0.32 c.c. of the reaction mixture due to reaction only for 254 μμ in *t* minutes; and *γ* = quantum efficiency.

Similar calculations were made in all the experiments and the results are summarised in Tables II to V. In the tables θ = 31° and λ = 254 μμ.

TABLE II.

Effect of varying the concentration of bromine.

*I*_{abs.} = 19.4 × 10¹³. *b* = 0.05M

<i>a</i> .	<i>k</i> ₀ × 10 ⁴ .	<i>γ</i> .
0.102M	22.6	11.8
0.075	22.3	8.8
0.054	23.6	6.8
0.037	20.6	3.6
0.025	20.6	2.6

TABLE III.

Effect of varying the concentration of cinnamic acid.

*I*_{abs.} = 34.4 × 10¹³. *a* = 0.05M.

<i>b</i> .	<i>k</i> ₀ × 10 ⁴ .	<i>γ</i> .
0.075M	60.4	7.5
0.05	40.2	5.2
0.0375	28.2	3.9
0.025	19.2	2.6

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From Table II we see that k_2 is independent of the initial concentration of bromine and from Table III, k_2 is proportional to the concentration of cinnamic acid.

TABLE IV.

Effect of varying the intensity of radiation absorbed by cinnamic acid.

$a = 0.05M.$		
$I_{abs.} \times 10^{-12}$.	$b.$	$k_2 \times 10^4.$
34.4	0.075M	60.4
14.2	"	24.0
34.4	0.05	40.2
14.2	"	16.4

TABLE V.

Effect of varying temperature.

$I_{abs.} = 34.4 \times 10^{12}. a = 0.05M.$			
$b.$	$k_2 \times 10^4$		$v.$
	$\theta = 32^\circ.$	$\theta = 41^\circ.$	
0.05M	40.2	60.9	1.5
0.025	19.2	29.0	1.5

From Table IV we see that k_2 is directly proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed by cinnamic acid. In Table V, v stands for temperature coefficient for 10° rise. From this table we see that the temperature coefficient of the reaction is of the order 1.5.

Reaction in Polarised Light.—The reaction was also carried out in plain polarised, *d*-circularly polarised and *l*-circularly polarised lights but no difference was observed in the behaviour of unpolarised, plane polarised and *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised lights. The velocity constant was found to be independent of the nature of polarisation of light. The description and the working principle of the polarising apparatus have been discussed in details by Ghosh *et al.* (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 495).

D I S C U S S I O N.

The reaction has the following characteristics:

(a) The reaction is unimolecular with respect to bromine as well as with respect to cinnamic acid; (b) there is no induction period; (c) the rate of reaction is directly proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed by cinnamic acid; (d) the temperature coefficient is 1.5; (e) the quantum efficiency is more than unity; (f) the rate of reaction is independent of the nature of polarisation of light.

The peculiar feature of this reaction is that the rate of reaction is directly proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed by cinnamic acid. Again the quantum efficiency is more than unity which indicates that the reaction is attended with some kind of chain formation. The following simple mechanism explains all the observed facts.

A molecule of cinnamic acid is activated by the absorption of a quantum of radiation of 254 $\mu\mu$. The activated cinnamic acid molecules may be deactivated either spontaneously or by collision with inert solvent molecules or with the walls of the containing vessel but may be stabilised by collision with unactivated cinnamic acid molecules. The dibromocinnamic acid molecules are formed when the activated cinnamic acid molecules collide with bromine molecules.

Thus

where C, C* and CBr₂ are the molecules of cinnamic acid, activated cinnamic acid and dibromocinnamic acid respectively.

The rate of formation of $C^* = I/E$, where $E = Nh\nu$. The rate of deactivation of C^* is directly proportional to the concentration of C (unactivated cinnamic acid molecules).

Thus the rate of deactivation of $C^* = \frac{k_2[C^*]}{[C]}$

$$[C^*] = \frac{I/E \cdot [C]}{k_2}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{d[Br_2]}{dt} &= k_3[C^*][Br_2] \\ &= k_3 \frac{I/E \cdot [C]}{k_2} \cdot [Br_2] \\ &= k^1 I/E \cdot [C][Br_2]. \end{aligned} \quad \dots (a)$$

The relation (a) agrees well with the experimental observation recorded in Tables I to IV that the rate of reaction is unimolecular with respect to both cinnamic acid and bromine and also that the rate is proportional to the intensity of radiation absorbed by cinnamic acid.

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